

Other materials

Educational Resources

Examples of citizen science
school-based approaches

Title

Cos4Cloud Citizen Science & Environmental Education for Sustainability - NKUA Six Educational Scenarios summary

About this resource

This **Six Educational Scenarios** summary was developed as a resource to support interest, in the development of **Educational Scenarios** that are part of citizen science-based environmental education activities and interventions. Educational Scenarios are part of Cos4Cloud's work on [education](#) led by Cos4Cloud project partner National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA) Environmental Education Lab. The [Cos4Cloud](#) project has developed thirteen technological services to help increase and improve the quantity and quality of observations. Cos4Cloud includes nine [Citizen Observatories \(COs\)](#). NKUA has [designed and demonstrated educational content](#) which can be adapted to support learning at primary, secondary or university level in Environmental Education (EE) and Educational Sustainable Development (ESD). This content showcases examples of citizen science school-based approaches that include examples demonstrating citizen observatories involved in Cos4Cloud and the use of project services.

This summary was compiled from NKUA documentation and incorporates contributions made by Greek Environmental Education teachers and school educational stakeholders as part of the co-design of educational scenarios in the context of the Cos4Cloud project. The main supporting resources and outputs were originally developed and delivered by NKUA in Greek and this resource is presented in English as part of the [Cos4Cloud Toolbox & Evidence Hub](#).

Cos4Cloud Education Lead Partner

Description

This Guide is provided as a guidance tool to support those interested in devising and implementing Citizen Science & Environmental Education for Sustainability educational scenarios and activities for use in schools and other educational settings using frameworks developed by NKUA.

The six Educational Scenarios were designed by NKUA for different school and educational settings across primary, secondary and University levels, using the Cos4Cloud Citizen Observatories (COs) and Services to provide key educational learning. They were initially designed for Greek based educational settings using [Pl@ntNet](#), [Natusfera](#) and [OdourCollect](#) and can be adapted for use in other educational settings using other Cos4Cloud Citizen Observatories (COs) Platforms and Services to support learning. This summary is presented as an Educational Resource in the [Cos4Cloud Toolbox & Evidence Hub](#).

Below are summary overviews of each of the six Educational Scenarios. See more about the Educational Scenarios and other Cos4Cloud educational approaches implemented by NKUA [here](#).

EDUCATIONAL SCENARIO 1

Educational Scenario 1 aims to familiarise students, who are in the last grades of primary school, with how to conduct citizen science with [Pl@ntNet](#) to study plant biodiversity in the field across two different environments: (a) the suburban forest of Ymittos (in the Attica region of Greece), and (b) their school garden.

The students learn to recognise various plant species and distinguish between endemic and invasive ones; they reflect on the factors affecting flora biodiversity (climate change, fires, deforestation, land appropriation, etc.); create a botanical guide and a botanical path; and make contact with representatives of the scientific community to build environmental awareness.

This scenario emphasises engagement and familiarisation of young learners with scientific research. [Pl@ntNet](#) is an integral part of the scenario and a tool to foster active citizenship in primary education students and open school education to the local community.

EDUCATIONAL SCENARIO 2

Educational Scenario 2 addresses the environmental issue of odour pollution in and around the school and the neighbourhoods around it. Primary school students are the target audience, and the focus is on connecting citizen science with Environmental Education (EE)/Education for Sustainable Development (ESD).

Based on an interdisciplinary approach and making use of [OdourCollect](#) the scenario aims to engage students with a range of learning activities with a playful and sensory experimentation approach. Students carry out sensory walks, keep odour diaries, create thematic maps, and critically consider the impact of unpleasant odours on people's socio-economic life and health, their interactions with other people and the ways they perceive their school environment.

During the implementation of this scenario, students are expected to become "agents of change" to promote sustainability in their school and local community. The pedagogical emphasis is on exploration (experience), cognition (awareness) and action. The scenario highlights and draws on the students' emotions and memories of smells in their school / neighbourhood, to propose an 'embodied learning' approach to citizen science.

EDUCATIONAL SCENARIO 3

Educational Scenario 3 aims to integrate citizen science into Environmental Education (EE) / Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) with the use of [Pl@ntNet](#) and [OdourCollect](#). It is aimed at students in the last years of primary education and invites them to engage in interdisciplinary activities including the creation of thematic maps, the construction of digital posters and cards and the formulation of their own proposal for the sustainable regeneration of a former industrial site, the Drapetsona Fertilizer and Chemical factory in Greece.

The scenario also tries to link scientific observations and measurements made with [Pl@ntNet](#) (for plant identification) and [OdourCollect](#) (for recording odours and air pollution incidents), with local history and popular culture perspectives and to integrate values and human rights concepts.

The scenario can also be adapted and used as part of a cross-curricular school garden action plan or in the context of an intercultural education project. The use of tools from two different citizen observatories to “map” the quality of the environment in an urban area of environmental concern emphasises interdisciplinarity, builds digital competence and an orientation towards action. It also seeks to establish links with intercultural education through environmental knowledge, local traditions, and popular culture.

EDUCATIONAL SCENARIO 4

Educational Scenario 4 aims to connect citizen science with Environmental Education (EE) / Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) using [Pl@ntNet](#) and [Natusfera](#). Through an interdisciplinary approach it engages secondary school students, teachers, institutions, and the academic community in various activities.

It focuses on turning the school garden into a learning environment, raises awareness of climate change as a biodiversity problem, points to individual and social responsibility for addressing it, talks about the need to create a favourable microclimate in school settings, engages students with designing a green fence to absorb noise and chemical pollution, initiates a school-based composting project and raises awareness in the school and the local community.

Through a combination of approaches and types of knowledge, this scenario aims to empower students to address current sustainability challenges through a scalable model of action that starts at their school. The school garden serves for experiential and collaborative learning based on the knowledge gained from using [Pl@ntNet](#) and [Natusfera](#).

EDUCATIONAL SCENARIO 5

Educational Scenario 5 looks at urban streams and creeks, which it describes as “isles of biodiversity” in the city. It focuses on the study of invasive/non-native species and the risks of ecosystem changes. High school students take on the role of researcher, photograph the plant species prevalent in a local stream at the Chalandri Creek in Greece, identify them via [Pl@ntNet](#), conduct a literature review search, and take a virtual tour of the area.

In addition to raising awareness of the ecological value of streams, the scenario has a key goal to integrate citizen science into Environmental Education (EE) / Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) by promoting practices that generate environmental knowledge and promote scientific research. It includes a visit to the Environmental Education Centre in Argyroupoli, Greece, which runs a similar educational project on streams (the Pikrodaphne stream). The scenario combines inquiry and experiential learning, focuses on the study and promotion of urban biodiversity, and emphasises the students' understanding and familiarisation with scientific research and the cultivation of their critical and inquiry thinking.

EDUCATIONAL SCENARIO 6

Educational Scenario 6 attempts to link citizen science with Environmental Education (EE)/Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) and oral history, based on the use of [OdourCollect](#); the International Citizens Observatory for Odours. Secondary school students, teachers, the local community, and other stakeholders are envisaged to engage in an interdisciplinary project to highlight the problem of odour pollution in contemporary cities through the collection of oral history narratives. In addition to this students construct a digital sensory map of place-based odours, which they enrich with local citizens stories. They also develop a sense of their local community's odours and become motivated to take the role of active citizens and identify local environmental problems. The aim is that students develop a competence to combine different genres of knowledge, such as measurements of environmental quality (via [OdourCollect](#)) with intergenerational stories from their community (via oral history) and integrate them to contextualise and pursue local sustainable development.

In addition, the students will construct a digital sensory map of place-based odours, which they will enrich with stories collected from local citizens. They will also develop a sense of the odours in their local community and become motivated to take on the role of active citizens and identify local environmental problems.

The aim is for students to develop the competence to combine different types of evidence, such as that from environmental quality measurements (through [OdourCollect](#)) with that from intergenerational stories collected from members of their community (through oral history) and integrate them into a whole to frame local sustainable development.

Conclusion

The summaries of Educational Scenarios, presented above, share case study examples from different school and educational settings in Greece, using some of the citizen observatories involved in Cos4Cloud: Pl@ntNet and Natusfera (on biodiversity) and OdourCollect (environmental monitoring). They focus on educational learning for either primary, secondary and university level students. The examples presented can also be adapted and applied using other [citizen observatories](#) across schools or a range of other educational settings in different countries.

Additional resources: [About the Cos4Cloud Toolbox and Evidence hub](#)

This guide is an educational resource that supports the development of Educational Scenarios based on a Template that is part of the citizen science and environmental education content and activities for schools developed by NKUA in the Cos4Cloud project (<https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/>). NKUA team authors: Maria Daskolia, Naya Grillia and Dimitris Gkatzos. **Title: Cos4Cloud Citizen Science & Environmental Education for Sustainability - NKUA Six Educational Scenarios summary.** This Guide is part of the Cos4Cloud Toolbox & Evidence Hub developed by the Open University in collaboration with project partners. Contact: cos4cloud-toolbox@open.ac.uk.

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